

A future with clean air..

Wish you were here?

Climate change – what's it all about?

Electricity and heating

Using more than we need

Our actions

Many of our daily actions result in burning fossil fuels – when we drive our cars, fire up a gas boiler, or use electricity from non-renewable sources

Food

Transport

A better future is possible – how will you play your part?

The consequences

These activities produce greenhouse gases like carbon emissions and methane. The gases form a layer which traps heat, increasing global temperatures and causing climate chaos

We need to change our behaviours now to reduce the impacts

Citizen's involvement

Striving for change

LOW

Dust-filled wasteland

HIGH

Citizens at the centre

HIGH

Heading for cleaner air

LOW

Air quality policy ambition

**A better future is possible -
how will you play your part?**

Are you breathing in clean air?

AIR POLLUTION

SOOT
DUST
PM_{2.5} PM₁₀

WE
BREATHE
IT IN

AND THIS
AFFECTS
OUR

WHO'S
AT
RISK

ALL OF US!

THE OLD

THE YOUNG

BUT ESPECIALLY...

PEOPLE WITH
HEALTH
CONDITIONS

WHAT AFFECTS
AIR POLLUTION?

SUPERMARKET

Welcome to ClairCity!

Dear

We are in class..... at
school. Today we have been exploring air
pollution and carbon emissions and the
problems they cause.

We are writing to tell you that.....

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.....
.....
.....

We learnt that.....

.....
.....

We would like if you could.....

.....
.....

Yours sincerely,

www.claircity.eu

Dear

Did you know air pollution leads to many health problems and is linked to around 300 deaths each year in Bristol? Poorer and BAME communities, the old, the young, and people with health conditions are the most impacted.

We know a better future is possible. That is why we ask you to take the following actions:

Yours sincerely,

Dear

Did you know air pollution leads to many health problems, especially for young people? Road traffic also produces carbon emissions, which cause climate change.

We know a better future is possible. That is why we are asking you to take the following actions:

Yours sincerely,
